

Turkification Islamisation and Modernisation in the Thought of Ziya Gökalp

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*This article examines the political philosophy of Ziya Gökalp (1876–1924), focusing primarily on his work *Türkleşmek, İslamlaşmak, Muasırlaşmak* (1918). Gökalp’s triadic framework of Turkification, Islamisation, and Modernisation is analysed as a potentially cohesive strategy for forging a modern Turkish identity. The study clarifies these concepts, emphasising their instrumental and contextual application, with Turkification as the ultimate goal and Islam and modernisation as complementary means. Prevailing interpretations often misrepresent Gökalp by conflating his early and later works or overlooking their historical context. This article challenges such views, arguing that Gökalp’s framing of Islam as a sociopolitical tool rather than strictly theological reconciles perceived tensions between secularism and religion. It also critiques Gökalp’s modernisation thesis, noting its pragmatism but highlighting its lack of specificity regarding institutional and technological reform. By positioning Gökalp as a tactician rather than a grand theorist, the article reemphasises his practical approach to achieving ‘Turkishness’ amidst the complexities of nationalism, religion, and modernity. This study contributes to Gökalp scholarship by revisiting his early works and advocating for context-driven analyses of Ottoman political thought, offering insights into enduring tensions within Turkish socio-political identity.*

CHAPTER I: INTRODUCTION

Widely considered the first Turkish sociologist, Ziya Gökalp (1876-1924) was an important figure in Turkish political thought (Berkes, 1936). The concepts of Turkism, Islamism, and modernism are central to his works. These concepts maintain their relevance now as much as they did during the tumultuous late Ottoman/early Republican period of Turkey. In this article, I wish to revisit this debate, which has become more prominent in 21st-century Turkey. Gökalp is significant to this debate because he is one of the defining figures surrounding these concepts. Scholarly interpretations vary significantly, with authors such as Heyd (1950) and Parla (1985) highlighting distinct tensions in Gökalp’s conceptual framework, whereas Topal (2017) emphasises historical contextualisation as key to understanding Gökalp’s integration of nationalism, Islam, and modernisation. However, commentary on the early period of Gökalp’s thought is nevertheless generally neglected. Much of this is owed to the fact that the newly formed Republic, under Atatürk, sought to suppress the idea of an Islamic-Turkish state. The current political climate in Turkey calls for a historical understanding of the frictions between Islam, laïcité, secularism, Turkishness, and other fundamental concepts and reflections on how Turkey and the Turkish people can reconcile these themes.

A number of Gökalp’s works published between 1913-14 in *İslam Mecmuası* and *Türk Yurdu* are collected to form the book *Türkleşmek İslamlaşmak Muasırlaşmak* (TIM, 1918), which will serve as the primary text of analysis in this article. This work will begin by taking a semantic approach. In the first section, I will seek to answer what Turkification, Islamisation, and modernisation – the triad – meant for Gökalp in a contextual setting. This is specifically necessary given that Gökalp uses these broad terms in an arguably esoteric manner. Inter-conceptual analysis becomes meaningless without establishing the ‘proper’ meaning Gökalp ascribes to these concepts. Scholarly discourse presents conflicting interpretations of Gökalp’s conceptual triad, with Heyd viewing Islam primarily as an instrument to Turkism, while Dodd (1979) positions Islam as foundational and indispensable. Clarifying Gökalp’s original meanings thus addresses existing analytical oversights in scholarship. First defining the terms independently, followed by their relation to each other, will allow us to unearth the philosophical underpinnings of Gökalp’s work, something Gökalp himself largely neglected to do (Parla, 1985).

Previous commentary regarding the possibility of their complementarity has not engaged sufficiently with all of Gökalp's work (Topal, 2017). Yet, Gökalp's political philosophy requires a foundational analysis of his entire corpus before any conclusion can be reached. I will argue that the triad of concepts is compatible, provided that certain preconditions are satisfied: understanding his heterodox view of Islam and establishing what it means to be Turkish. Most importantly, one needs to acknowledge Gökalp as a product of his time, taking into account the wide-ranging nature of his works, including his poetry.

After discussing the relationship between the concepts and the implied philosophies which come with it, I will evaluate the practical viability of Gökalp's thought within his historical context. This will be done by establishing whether some of the concepts defined are at odds with one another, utilising an inter-conceptual approach. This critique, however, will not be the central issue considered in this article. Instead, the main argument I present against Gökalp concerns the friction regarding his underlying philosophy. I will, however, conclude that these critiques are not as relevant as they might appear, as we ought to classify Gökalp foremost as a tactician rather than a 'grand-plan' theorist. Fundamentally, this article will argue that Gökalp's triad of Turkification, Islamisation, and modernisation is fully reconcilable, but only when viewed through the lens of his distinctive, heterodox understanding of Islam as a predominantly social phenomenon and his fundamentally pragmatic approach to nationalism. Recognising these conditions clarifies apparent contradictions and demonstrates that Gökalp's triad coherently serves a unified political project rather than disparate ideological aims.

CHAPTER II: ABOUT GÖKALP

Understanding Gökalp's triad of Turkification, Islamisation, and modernisation requires first placing him within his intellectual and historical setting. This section examines his formative influences, particularly the legacy of the Tanzimat reforms, to illustrate how his thought developed in response to the failures of late Ottoman modernisation. Gökalp was born in Diyarbakır in 1876, towards the end of the Ottoman Empire's centuries-old reign. His formative education followed the failed Tanzimat reforms of the 19th century. The Tanzimat reforms aimed to 'modernise' the laws of the Ottoman Empire, aligning them with the legislation of other contemporaneous European powers (Hussain, 2011). Gökalp, writing after their failure, attempted to formulate his vision of a modern empire using the lessons of the Tanzimat as a foundation for his reforms. At a time when overtly secular, reformatory, and revolutionary authors were being persecuted, such as Namık Kemal (Toprak, 2008), Gökalp's thought was formed by an acute awareness of this peril.

Placing Gökalp within a specific tradition of political philosophy is important, but doing so is not straightforward. Interpretations of how Gökalp should be classified differ, with approaches ranging from understanding his theory within a purely Turkish sphere to a strictly European derivation, and various combinations of both. The merit of such a classification is that it allows a comparative perspective into areas of his thought motivated and inspired by multiple traditions. The study of Ottoman political thought has often been neglected compared with other West Asian thought; since Ottoman thinkers did not produce as many innovative theories of governance, society, and state, they tend not to be considered genuine political theorists. What Sariyannis (2018) describes as 'local Orientalism' has also pervaded discourse regarding Ottoman political theory. Academics of West Asia participated in perpetual comparisons between the giants of Arab Islamic thought, such as Ibn Sina and Ibn Khaldun, to more understated authors. While it is true that there were few radical, grand-plan theorists, with notable exceptions such as Çelebi, this does not mean that grand-plan theorists should be disregarded nor does this mean that Ottoman and Turkish political thought lacks value, but rather they formulated their corpus primarily utilising distinctive methodological principles.

What is unique about Gökalp's thought, which is also original in terms of Ottoman/Turkish political thought, is his systematic study of society. Berkes (1954) describes Gökalp as the first Turkish sociologist. This is not to say Turkish sociology did not exist before Gökalp, but sociological studies derived purely from a Turkish setting were not previously conducted. In Gökalp's case, the use of sociology in formulating his political thought evidently comes from a distinctly European tradition. Here, we can understand why some deem Gökalp's ideas as being derivative of European political and social thought (see Parla, 1985; Malczewski, 2018). Gökalp was inspired by Durkheim, for example, in the culture/civilisation dichotomy (Nefes, 2013), yet it would be reductive to simplify the entirety of his thought as derivative of Durkheim. Instead, Gökalp recognised the essential aspects of Durkheimian classification but was able to apply it to the unique conditions within which the Turkish nation found itself.

Understanding Gökalp as taking part in the European style of social study alongside an awareness of an inherently Turkish reformatory practice allows us to better conceptualise his political thought. The issues present in 21st-century and contemporary Turkey can ultimately trace their roots to Gökalp's time and beyond; this is why revisiting Gökalp in the current sociopolitical climate is essential. Gökalp foreshadowed in his works the friction that might occur between the idea of a republic and a religious nation, so much so that he states that “[i]f a nation truly wants to be a modern nation, the first condition is the separation of religious affairs from state affairs” (Gökalp, 1923, p. 85). By looking back at the foundations of secular republican thought in Turkey, I hope to add to the much-needed illumination of Turkish political thought. The rationale for focusing on TIM is two-fold. First, much of the scholarship on Gökalp disproportionately focuses on his later works, primarily *The Principles of Turkism* (1923). This neglects some relatively novel and influential writings that Gökalp wrote in the early 20th century. Secondly, Gökalp's TIM has become more relevant to the current Turkish political landscape. The ruling AK Party has been introducing increasingly Islamist policies for the past two decades that, at times, have clashed with the immutable first three articles of the Turkish constitution. Gökalp demonstrates in TIM the unique interaction between these challenging concepts that Turkey and the Turkish people have been wrestling with for the past century, whilst recognising the complex relationship between Turkism, Islam, and modernism.

CHAPTER III: GÖKALP'S AIM

Gökalp was not merely theorising about nationalism—he had a specific vision for the Turkish nation and its future. This section sets out what that vision was, comparing his nationalism to Weber's ideas on identity and statehood. Doing so makes it possible to assess how Gökalp saw nationalism as an instrument rather than an end in itself. As such, it is first vital to establish what Gökalp considered as his end goal for the Turkish nation and the Turkish state. To draw a comparison, I liken Gökalp to Weber. Weber, in his earlier writings, advocated for economic nationalism (Palonen, 2001). Much like Gökalp, Weber opposed and criticised nationalist ideas based on a necessary predicate of race. Although Weber opposed essentialist or collectivist ideas, he was a staunch nominalist who valued the importance of nationhood and the nation (Palonen, 2001). The Turkish Islamic modern state was a normative desire of Gökalp, and he believed in its objective necessity. Similar to the idea of the German people we see in Weber's work (Palonen, 2001), I argue that Gökalp's understanding of nationality interacting with religion, an international community, and 'civilisation' is applicable beyond the Turkish nation. What does it mean to be in an international community? What does it mean to be modernised? What does it mean to be religious? These are all valid questions that Gökalp raises in the context of the Turkish people, which are also pertinent to a wide range of countries and eras. As such, when reading what follows, it is imperative to consider that, for Gökalp, nationalism was foremost an instrumental tool for his underlying political philosophy of harmony, social order, and cohesion. I justify the choice of outlining these underlying philosophies on the basis of his pragmatic approach. This pragmatism allowed him to conceptualise best the avenues for the development of the Turkish people. For the reasons to be discussed below, Gökalp found this within Turkish nationalism.

CHAPTER IV: WHAT IS 'ISLAMISATION'?

Gökalp's treatment of Islam is neither straightforward nor conventional. This section examines his understanding of Islamisation, arguing that he saw religion as primarily a social force rather than a theological necessity. This distinction is crucial to understanding how Islam interacts with the other elements of his triad. Since Gökalp only discusses Islamism within the context of 'pure' Islam, this section of conceptual definitions is particularly intricate. What follows will show that Gökalp's understanding of Islam is both heterodox and concerned more with its political implications. It is not appropriate to dissect whether that which is considered as Sufism, not-Sufism, Islamic legalism, etc., truly reflects their theological foundations; the important aspect here is their perception and political implications. By also looking at some of Gökalp's poetic literature and works related to Islam, we find evidence that explains what Islam means for him within this cultural form. This must be done by also considering his earlier works. What we can therefore conclude from an analysis of various roots is that Gökalp understood Islam as more social than religious.

Gökalp's belief in the influence of Islam in formulating the identity of Turkishness is evident. Some elements, however, require clarification: a) how did Gökalp arrive at this specific idea and role of Islam, especially regarding the theological justifications and their respective influences on the formulation of his “Modern Islamic Turkish community” (Gökalp, 1916, p. 11); and b) is Islam an absolute end for Gökalp, or

just a means to the end of Turkification? To answer the first question, we need to look at a variety of ways in which Islam impacted Gökalp and his politics, ranging from an understanding of the Sufi tradition, the Caliphate as the centre of Ottoman nationalism, and Islamic culture as containing 'foreign' elements.

We need to consider Gökalp's relationship with Sufism to answer the first question. Sufism tends to be described as Islam's esoteric, mystic side (Cook, 2015). The perception of Sufism assists Gökalp's theory as it tends to be treated "as a holistic and transcendent philosophy... [which] provides Muslims greater latitude to engage in debates" (Whyte, 2014, para. 17), meaning it is able to provide Gökalp with flexibility in fitting Islam into his thought. Though this interpretation of Sufism may invite theological dispute, it remains an incontrovertible fact that such was its usual perception and political manifestation. It is also important to note here that Sufism does not have an exclusive claim to truth in Islam, and it was certainly not always the norm of Islamic practice in the Ottoman Empire. Based on this, we require context on this form of Islam and its influence on Gökalp's thought. Gökalp's esotericism and Sufism were influenced by Yunus Emre, an important mystic in Turkish Sufi culture (Köprülü, 1976). Yunus Emre's poetry, characterised by its non-dogmatic, community-oriented interpretation of Islam, resonates deeply within Gökalp's verse, demonstrating continuity in their shared conception of religion primarily as a social construct. For example, in his poem 'Vatan' (1918), Gökalp envisions a nation united through shared religious practices that are culturally meaningful and linguistically accessible, illustrated in his lines: "in Turkish the call to prayer is said, / The meaning of his prayer the villager can understand" (Gökalp, 1918, p. 23). This framing of religion as culturally rooted and communally binding parallels Yunus Emre's earlier poetic philosophy, where Islam similarly transcends dogmatic confines to emphasise communal love and spiritual unity. Emre explicitly rejects conflict and doctrinal rigidity, writing: "I did not come to life for war, / My duty is only love [...] / I came to build hearts" (Emre, as cited in Köprülü, 1976, p. 122). Thus, Gökalp's vision of religion aligns significantly with Emre's mystically inflected social ethics, positioning faith primarily as a vehicle for social solidarity and collective identity, rather than theological prescription. Another poem that exemplifies this dimension of Islamic mysticism is as follows:

Neither far am I (from You) nor near,
I am disheartened and bewildered.
I cannot part company, so used am I (to You)
Let us be friends again, my God"
(Gökalp, 1918, trans. Heyd, 1954)

Gökalp's works of poetry are reflective of both invoking the mythological concept of a united Turkish nation and interlaying it with Islamic commentary. To understand how Gökalp saw Islam within a political setting, we need to contrast it with Islam's political function during Gökalp's time.

The governance of the Ottoman Empire relied on its own unique interpretation of sharia law (Katz, 2009). Islamic jurisprudence was derived from multiple sources, namely, *kanun* (dynastic law), *sharia* (religious law), and *sultanic law* (Katz, 2009). These legal sources, especially the particular interpretation of sharia, conflicted with Gökalp's understanding of the position of Islam in law and governance, even with the legal reforms of the 18th and 19th Centuries. Gökalp instead considered Islam within a Sufi framework. Topal (2017) notes that Gökalp saw the "institutionalised legalistic approach to Islam as part of the problem," and recognising this strict legalised version, Gökalp sought "refuge in Sufi tradition which resonate[d] with his desire for an organic fraternal community" (Topal, 2017, p. 27).

This 'fraternal community' develops from Gökalp's belief in the importance of *örf* and a temporally conceived form of understanding Islam. *Örf* can be translated as custom or tradition, but in this context, a socio-religious tradition. Heyd argues that the implication of this was that Gökalp saw Islam as a "historical phenomenon subject to change and dependent on the social circumstances in which it [Islam] developed" (Heyd, 1950, p. 83). Gökalp was also influenced by Abu Yusuf, who had said that "customary law (*örf*) was to be preferred to Koranic command or prohibition" (Heyd, 1950, p. 84). With this motivation, Gökalp's idea of Islam centred around the idea that the "conscience of the Islamic community expressed in customary ways of living was in nature divine," and furthermore that it "became possible to claim that the social element in Islam could have even greater validity with regard to social and temporal matters" (Heyd, 1950, p. 87). Islam was not to be considered in its strictly ecclesiastical form, as in the Ottoman Empire, but rather primarily in a communitarian social, yet also personal, form. Gökalp emphasised Islam as a social tool rather than a strict dogma. Gökalp's

secularism, in the strict sense of separation between state and religion, was also evident in his later works, although his earlier works lack clarity on this position. This is especially true given that Gökalp still placed the Turkish nation as the torchbearer of a global Islamic ummah in TIM (Gökalp, 1918, p. 51).

This radically heterodox interpretation of Islam allowed Gökalp greater freedom to explore the role that Islam has in his understanding of Turkish nationalism. The freedom from the Quranic and Hadith traditions, both of which are divine sources prescribing the conjoining of religion and politics, allowed Gökalp to conceptualise a more malleable form of Islam. Gökalp's interpretation allowed him the liberty that orthodox interpretations could not offer him, such as potentially contradicting Hadith doctrine, which may have been a conscious decision to ensure flexibility for his political philosophy. This application of the concept of *örf* as justification for Turkish nationalism is important. Heyd's (1950) commentary on this describes the niche that Islam was to fit in for Gökalp. Heyd (1950, p. 99) argues that Gökalp did not believe Islam "could neither properly constitute a civilisation nor hinder any Islamic nation from joining whatever civilisation it wished." Heyd's interpretation is clear: Islam is not a necessary condition for Gökalp's vision of the Turkish nation.

Establishing Gökalp's view of Islam removed from its context, as we have done hitherto, is rather straightforward. However, issues arise when we have to understand Islam within the aim of Turkification. While there are other interpretations of Gökalp's view of Islam, what has so far been discussed is sufficient to formulate a more nuanced, contextualised, and thorough interpretation. Quranic and Hadith traditions, serving as the divine source, meant, in theory, it was possible to differentiate between culture and religion. Islam was considered originally 'pure', and importing foreign cultures through the medium of Islam is what Gökalp considered dangerous. This presents a paradox: Gökalp both claimed Quranic and Hadith traditions as providing the basis to purify Islam and wanted to 'purify' Islam from them (with the usage of *örf*). In addition, a decentralised system of religious governance allowed Gökalp, theoretically, as much legitimacy as other bodies of divine authority. As Heyd (1950, p. 86) rightfully points out, such a project provided "a theoretical basis for an almost boundless 'purification' of the Muslim religion." Divine doctrine, which contradicted the temporally formulated, was to be rejected, and the cultural components deemed alien were to be removed with the pretext of divine doctrine. While this purification ostensibly claimed to remove culture (leaving a pure Islam), it was actually a project to imbue the faith with Turkish culture. This purification, therefore, did not focus on theological validity but on using Islam as a means to Turkism. Still, Gökalp's radical views on Islam are not reflected in his reform proposals; for example, he makes very superficial critiques of the Caliphate. Heyd (1950, p. 87) attributes this to the fact that Gökalp "did not dare to do [renounce the Caliphate] so openly but tried to modify its powers without changing its name."

With his self-censorship, to further understand Gökalp's thoughts regarding Islam, we need to understand his poetry and literature, something that the present scholarship has largely failed to do while considering TIM as well. The definitional issue we face here is that there tends to be a disjuncture between what Gökalp's 'political' and 'personal' Islam looked like. As mentioned, some of this disconnect can be attributed to the censorship during the Ottoman era; legally, the renunciation of the Caliphate mandated capital punishment. The implication here for Gökalp is notable, as it means we need to understand his thoughts on Islam with a degree of self-censorship. Similarly, the main text this article focuses on, TIM, was censored in the Republican era for its overt enunciation of the unity needed between Turkism and Islam. As such, the present scholarship understands Gökalp's poetry and literature based on assumptions derived from *The Principles*, ignoring the contemporaneously written TIM.

For Gökalp, religion was primarily an identity marker. For example, Gökalp (1918, p. 11) elucidates this when he states that "a Turk can offer his daughter to an Arab, an Albanian, a Kurd, a Circassian. But he can never give her to a Finn or a Christian Hungarian." The significance of this statement is that, unlike Huntington-esque classifications of civilisations, Gökalp viewed the Turkish people as part of European civilisations but also recognised their religious affiliations with ethnic groups such as Arabs and Persians, highlighting the significance he placed on Islam. This contradicts Heyd's position, who argues that Gökalp saw Islam as tangentially important at best. Critically, it is important to note that whether Islam had a heavier weighting in Gökalp's triad or was subsumed by other concepts is not a simple issue. Instead, we must understand this phenomenon through the Durkheimian influence on

Gökalp. Pearce's (2012, p. 410) commentary on this topic presents this position, arguing that "Gökalp envisioned that the new nation would replace religion in the collective consciousness, but that the religion of Islam would be a partner in supporting that move toward national consciousness." This understanding of Gökalp's relationship with Islam works well, as it does not open the issue of classifying Gökalp to be either 'pro' or 'anti' Islam. Instead, it situates Gökalp within a specific tradition. Based on this view, I interpret Gökalp as a radical reformer. He recognised that the national consciousness would be far too tenuous during the reforms he proposed. Hence, he saw Islam as the means to maintain solidarity in nationhood and thus proposed a role for it in his idea of Turkism.

CHAPTER V: WHAT IS 'TURKIFICATION'?

Turkification, for Gökalp, was never a question of race. This section clarifies what he meant by the term, contrasting it with the racial nationalist ideas circulating at the time. Understanding this distinction is central to assessing how his vision of Turkishness functioned within the broader triad. Out of the three concepts I am to define in this article, Turkification also has a unique place insofar as its definition is more easily formulated by a negative definition, i.e. defining what it is not. This is largely due to the racialised conceptions of Turkishness that dominated nationalist discourse in the 20th century. Üzer's (2016) commentary is important in contextualising different Turkish nationalist ideas, sketching their historical roots. He begins by considering the variances between Akçura and Gökalp; the former "attached more importance to ethnicity" (Üzer, 2016, p. 55). Akçura, a contemporary of Gökalp, championed the removal of the millet system of multi-ethnoreligious civil jurisdictions and was vocal about the need for forced assimilation of non-Turks (Poulton, 1997). Critically, Gökalp is rightfully recognised as minimising the importance of ethnic and racial roots, instead focusing on "the cultural foundations of nation-making" (Üzer, 2016, p. 55). Gökalp's definition of Turkishness did not contain references to race, but similar to Akçura, Gökalp believed in the importance of assimilation of foreign cultures into Turkish culture. For Gökalp, however, this was not necessarily a violent assimilation. Rather, it was an idea predicated upon the vitality of the state having to exist within a nationalist framework. Ethnic Turkish nationalism was further popularised by Nihal Atsız and others. Atsız's writings on a racialised form of Turkish nationalism are contemporaneous with the development of movements such as the Young Wolves—a neo-fascist organisation—and the penetration of prominent ultra-nationalist figures into Turkish politics in the later 20th century, such as Alparslan Türkeş.

This view of the singular nation is contrasted with Ottoman nationalism, which centred around the concept of the Sultan, who, as the divinely ordained caliph, would be the leader of the global ummah. The nation was a religious phenomenon, not a cultural one. This form of nationalism is evident in the way the Ottoman legal system recognised those who inhabited Ottoman lands. Those of a Muslim faith would be citizens, and others would be classified as subjects. Notably, this division was not based on an understanding of nativity nor of race (Kaya, 2021). To give a crude example, an Albanian Muslim in the Ottoman Empire would have more rights in the state than a Turkish Jew. The Ottoman Empire was an Islamic empire. Considering Gökalp within the historical context of these thinkers is important for the scholarship, as it forces a reconsideration of erroneously labelling Gökalp wholly within either of these traditions.

Gökalp's early writings can be interpreted as conflicting with his later works, especially regarding the prominence of Islam, its role, and its functions, if any, in a modern Turkish state. However, taken as a whole, his writings indicate that the establishment of a Turkish state was the primary impetus for all his broader philosophical framework. This is indicative of the weighting he intended to place on the process of Turkification. Yet, even with this evidently clear goal, it is still important to establish what the Turk in Turkishness was to be. In evaluating what it means to be Turkish, Gökalp presents us with a challenging quotation to unpack: "the Turkish nation is a community belonging to the Ural-Altai family, the Islamic ummah, and the European international community" (Gökalp, 1918, p. 11). When deconstructing this, we can find Turkishness, and therefore Turkification, as comprising a multitude of symbiotic relationships between varying concepts. The Durkheimian dichotomy of culture vis-à-vis civilisation is equally present. While this characterisation aids in elucidating the meaning of Turkishness within the context of various groups to which the Turkish nation belongs, Gökalp posits a contentious assertion that Dodd (1979) examines. Gökalp (1918, p. 12) makes a strong statement before the previous quote, where he notes that "[a]s soon as the idea of Turkification was born, the need for Islamisation began to be felt." Dodd argues that Gökalp's understanding of Islam is contradictory, as Islam was a personal affair for Gökalp. Conversely, Dodd notes the social functions

that Gökalp ascribes to Islam, arguing that the role of Islam was overstated in his theory. Dodd's position is best summarised by Davison (1995, p. 198): "Gökalp's emphasis on Islam within his trinity was too strong [...] The problem was [...] Gökalp wanted to limit religion to the sphere of private conscience even though he 'found its vitality' in society."

However, Dodd's characterisation of Turkism is largely an oversimplification that fails to adequately consider the context of Gökalp's writings. Gökalp's nationalism must be compared to Ottoman nationalism, purely due to the period in which he was writing. Gökalp, working within this paradigm, made a radical proposition of Turkism without the necessary involvement of Islam, recognising that Turkishness was not inherently Islamic. Nevertheless, adopting a pragmatic perspective, Gökalp acknowledged that demarcating what constitutes Turkish identity and what is inherently Islamic would prove to be a formidable endeavour. Similarly, Gökalp understood that such a radical proposal would be met with disapproval by a majoritarily Muslim population. The 'purification' that Gökalp wanted from Islam, to establish what is 'truly Turkish', would be a challenging task. In recognising this, Gökalp opts for a proposal to remove the 'alien' components of Islam. Dodd's argument that Islam was the predominant and the main concept within Gökalp's triad does not consider the historic relationship between Turkism and Islam. Yet it also must be noted that Gökalp frequently critiques the values of Islam that he saw as alien to the values held by the Turkish nation (Daglyer, 2007). Islam was not so much valuable as a theological necessity in Turkism, but rather to be considered in the Durkheimian manner: as a social tool. Hence, there is no issue of contradiction, as the way Gökalp understood Islam makes recognising the important personal component of Islam and its 'social vitality' not mutually exclusive.

A more nuanced approach is presented by Arai, who understands that the interaction of Islam with Turkism/Turkishness is not straightforward. Arai comments that "Turkish nationalists did not necessarily pursue secularisation for Westernisation; they were rather in favour of Islamisation" (Arai, 1992, p. 97). Arai's comprehension of the issue certainly surpasses that of Dodd, as it reflects an understanding of the inherent complexities involved in delineating what should be classified as 'Islamic' versus what is 'Turkish.' Although Arai qualifies this by suggesting that such Islamisation was "a means of regaining the original truth of Islamic" (Arai, 1992, p. 101), it ultimately appeals to a definition of Turkism that is confined within the parameters of Islam, a position with which Gökalp firmly disagreed. Even in his later works, Gökalp recognised the significance of Islam, positioning it, in concordance with language, as one of the defining hallmarks of Turkism. However, I do not think classifying Islam as the defining trait of Turkification is true to Gökalp's work. Therefore, we need to understand Gökalp's vision of Turkism in a form largely not discussed in the literature. A modified version of Arai's argument, as presented below, establishes what Gökalp truly meant by being a Turk when considering his earlier works within their context.

Gökalp frequently references the Ural-Altai understandings of Turkism, with Turks having their roots and homeland as being in Central Asia (Gökalp, 1923), plainly indicating that he considers the idea of Turkism as more closely associated with the idea of Turanism than a global Islamic ummah. This is further supported by the chapter On Turan in *The Principles*. While it is true that holding both values is not mutually exclusive, it has to be maintained that many of the traditions that Gökalp sought to restore do not have their roots in Islamic practices, as Arai notes, but rather in traditional Turkic/Turkish practices. In this respect, it is out of necessity that Gökalp appeals to elements of Islam in defining aspects of Turkishness, rather than a normative desire. The connection between Turkishness and Islam was far too entrenched for there to be a complete removal of Islam. As referenced above, Gökalp had strong disagreements with the values of Islam that contradicted what he considered to be Turkish. Owing to censorship and restrictions on freedom of expression, outright critiques of Islam would be difficult for Gökalp. Thus, his critique centred around "promoting an authentic Turkish morality" (Daglyer, 2007, p. 60) instead of an overt criticism of Islam. An example of his critique is as follows: "[a]mong the ancient Turks, religion was free from strict ceremonies, perverse forms of worship [...] it made them very tolerant towards women and other nations" (Gökalp, 1923, pp. 51-53). Daglyer reads this post-Ottoman Gökalp as "implicitly criticizing the Islamic tradition as a source of corruption" (Daglyer, 2007, p. 60). In this regard, we see that Gökalp saw the idea of the Turkish nation as being associated with and formulated from a Turanist principle. Indeed, such propositions are elucidated much more vividly in *The Principles*. The scholarship unanimously agrees with the Turanist views of Gökalp; a very popular poem from Gökalp representing this pan-Turanist ideology is as follows:

Vatan is neither Turkey for the Turks, nor Turkistan;
 Vatan is a great and eternal country: Turan!
 (Gökalp, 1914)

However, it is notable that the early Gökalp understands Turanism as an important ideology, yet one that is distinctive from the idea of a Turkish nation. Only in his later works do we see the concept of nationhood as being a Turanic concept take a more prominent position. In fact, in *TİM*, Gökalp denounces this idea indirectly, where he states that we ought to understand the Turkic people under the term race which is classified by “a group of people with similarities” (Gökalp, 1918, p. 55). Gökalp then continues to understand that the nation is characterised by *lisan-i aileyi* (a familial language), that being Istanbul Turkish (Gökalp, 1918, pp. 54-57). In this case, Gökalp then continues to elaborate that while the Turkic people have similarities to each other, their language and ‘tribal’ differences lead Gökalp to believe they should comprise their own states. If a country is “not the homeland of a nationality, it becomes an almshouse where individuals can feed themselves to gluttony” (Gökalp, 1918, p. 57). Therefore, we see that Gökalp’s understanding of nationhood changed across the years and it is simplistic to argue that he was a pan-Turanist, in the way we find him in *The Principles*, within all of his works.

In sum, Gökalp’s views on Turkism can be understood as follows. Gökalp reluctantly appealed to Islam in some form for his Turkism, as he understood that Turkism itself evolved following the Seljuk’s (the spiritual predecessors of the Ottoman Empire) adoption of Islam. Critically, this was not a subsummation. Instead, it was understood as a composite aspect of Turkish culture. Evidently, in areas where the incorporation of Islamic values and culture contravened what was to be considered Turkish, Gökalp explicitly rejected these values and appealed to a ‘true’ understanding of Turkishness. It is evident that Turkishness did not pertain to racialised theories, a point that can be substantiated with relative ease, as Gökalp explicitly rebukes the claims of ethno-nationalist authors (Gökalp, 1923). Gökalp’s rejection of a racialised Turkish identity is also evident in how Gökalp believes the Ottoman Empire should treat non-Turkish subjects; a modern empire required the inclusion of all its subjects, from the Balkans to the Sinai. Gökalp notes in *The Principles* that “the nation cannot be defined by racial, tribal, geographic [...] terms” (Gökalp, 1923, p. 19). This is not to say, however, that a proposal for cultural homogenisation of non-Turks was not apparent in his work. Turkism was the spearhead upon which the remainder of his political philosophy was to follow. As such, the liberty he had in defining concepts to his leisure is only apparent in this part of the triad.

CHAPTER VI: WHAT IS ‘MODERNISATION’

Modernisation was necessary, but not at any cost. Gökalp’s approach was to reject blind imitation of the West while still recognising that technological and institutional advancement was unavoidable. This section explores how he balanced this tension and why modernisation, for him, was inseparable from Turkification. In theory, Gökalp does not provide a contentious description of modernisation that requires further explanation. The contention point in this section arises when we examine this project of modernisation alongside other concepts in Gökalp’s thought.

Since its declining fortunes in European theatres, the Ottoman Empire had concerned itself greatly with attempts at modernisation, Westernisation, and similar projects to ensure its survival in the face of decline. Thinkers across the 18th and 19th centuries formulated theories on how to ‘modernise’, whatever this entailed for each theorist. Writers such as Atıf Mustafa Efendi emphasised the importance of returning to an orthodox understanding of Islam in reforming the Ottoman Empire and that a departure from Islamic governance was the cause of the issues facing the Ottoman Empire (Sariyannis, 2019). Conversely, thinkers such as İbrahim Müteferrika argued that reformation should occur on Western principles, even going as far as to argue that “military reforms [should be] based on an acknowledgement of the superiority of European armies” (Sariyannis, 2019, p. 385). To critique the sanctity of the Ottoman army during this time was radical and, in effect, shows how thinkers struggled with defining modernisation. Gökalp attempts, instead of these, to formulate a system that is compatible with all of the conflicting demands that the Ottoman, and later, Turkish people had.

Ascertaining what this modernisation means is best done when contrasted with the Tanzimat reforms. This is particularly useful as it allows us to consider modernisation within the context of previous attempts and to recognise the manner in which Gökalp wanted to tackle this project differently. Gökalp argues that “[m]odernisation for us, today, means being able to build and use dreadnoughts, automobiles, aeroplanes like the Europeans; modernisation does not mean resembling the Europeans in form and livelihood”

(Gökalp, 1918, p. 11). While this statement seemingly provides a substantive definition, it merits discussion of what this would be in practice.

Gökalp points out the lacking technological advancements of the Ottomans compared to their European counterparts. The Industrial Revolution in Continental Europe dramatically affected the Ottomans, acting as a contributing factor to the collapse of the Empire in 1921 (Clark, 1954). Modernisation, therefore, was not an optional ideology for the Ottomans and the subsequent Republic but a matter of survival. Attempts at modernisation throughout the Ottoman Empire largely failed, where the adoption of Western systems of governance, considered at the time as synonymous with modernisation, was constructed upon ill foundations. The Gülhane Edict (1839) was a step in the modernisation process of the Empire. While covering a large series of reforms, such as the bureaucratisation of the workforce and tax reforms in line with laissez-faire economic policies, the key aspects of Gökalp's thought were those concerning rights and nationhood, such as the universalisation of the law of the land. The millet concept was abolished. This system allowed multitudes of civil governance under the Empire so that nationalities within the borders of the Empire could govern themselves in civil matters with relative independence. The Edict, however, abolished this and adopted, as Continental Europe was doing, a universal national law. Paradoxically, this is regarded as one of the first steps towards overall secularisation in the Empire, as the supremacy of one singular law was applied to all (even though this law was Sharia), deviating from the concept of self-governance developed in traditional Islamic jurisprudence (Davison, 1990). Gökalp looked favourably upon the abolition of the millet system, as he argued that the Turkish nation should comprise a singular Turkish culture. Further reforms, such as the Reform Edict of 1856 under Abdulmajid I, brought about reforms which tend to be described as secular, yet they were not motivated by secular ideals, having been written mostly under duress by France and Britain, following the Crimean War (Gülsoy, 1999). This represents a modernisation within a Western framework rather than within a Turkish understanding, for which Gökalp argues, even though he agreed with these secular reforms.

While Gökalp viewed these reforms positively, he believed these took place with the wrong actualisation. Gökalp (1918) notes that the reforms of the Tanzimat were “born of genuine needs” (Gökalp, 1918, p. 15), but that when these reforms actualised, they “produced extremely harmful results for the state's peoples and especially for Turks” (Gökalp, 1918, p. 18). Indeed, reformation in industry and government was required, but many of these modernising policies brought on an emulation of Western culture alongside them. This was a particular issue which Gökalp did not want to reoccur when proposing his modernisation project. Beyond this, Gökalp was critical of the Tanzimat reforms attempt to create a supra-national system of identity, noting that “no one except the Tanzimat-supporting Turks accepted the new meaning of the term ‘Ottoman’” (Gökalp, 1918, p. 18).

A notable example of how reformatory practices before Gökalp were more about Westernisation than necessarily modernisation is the Nizam-i Cedid reforms under Mahmud II in 1829. These were aimed at modernising the Ottoman military and had wider implications for Ottoman society. One of the reforms adopted the fez as compulsory headwear for soldiers instead of the traditional Ottoman turban, adopting Western styles. As Shaw (1965) notes, this radical transformation was seen as a movement of adopting Western values as well as their practices. Further radical transformations are indicative of Westernisation, as opposed to the modernisation sans Westernisation that Gökalp envisioned. Although the reforms were largely deemed a failure, Gökalp used this as an example of how not to modernise.

Therefore, how could Gökalp understand reform when faced with decades of similarly motivated yet failed reforms? Scholarship analysing Gökalp's triad of thought tends to consider his modernisation thesis at surface level, but it is evident that a deeper analysis is required. Consider the following from TIM:

On the one hand, we should endeavour to become a nation with history and tradition, and on the other hand, we should endeavour to formulate philosophies that lay claim to develop sciences resilient [in the face of other] science and industry, and to create philosophies that are constantly inspired by methods (Gökalp, 1918, p. 15).

Here, we see Gökalp's desire not simply to adopt the principles of modernisation of the West and depart from its philosophies, but rather independently develop a philosophical foundation for the project of modernisation in the future. He is explicit that this is not a case of adopting sciences from the West as they develop, but rather that the modern Islamic-Turkish nation needs to “infuse and blend the science and philosophy of the period, and the sciences and methodology [of the period], and our religious

traditions” (Gökalp, 1918, p. 19). Yet the exact way in which Gökalp considers this modernisation is not elucidated by him. We must thus pose the question: what actual functional changes need to be made differently than what had previously been tried in the Ottoman period of reformation? It is possible to simply argue that Gökalp intended to make those practically similar reforms of the 19th century but without cultural importation as well. However, this raises the further question of why the reforms that were not concerned with cultural issues like taxation and bureaucratic reformation, failed. This is an area in which Gökalp does not provide enough commentary.

What is, however, notable in TIM in relation to modernisation is the mention of Kızıl Elma. This is the only time that the mythic, utopic vision of this concept is mentioned explicitly in the entirety of the text. Kızıl Elma refers to the Oghuz Turk mythological conception of a far-away metaphorical land where all Turkic people will be joined together (Hür, 2015). After explaining the Turkish vision of technological advancement, Gökalp makes an uncharacteristically ambitious statement: “[t]his [after reform] is when we reach the homeland that the people’s spirit seeks as the Kızıl Elma, and we will be free in the real sense of the word and independent in civilisation” (Gökalp, 1918, p. 20). What is particularly important here is how Gökalp noted that, in the future, the Turkish civilisation will be actualised independently of Western civilisation, despite his initial proposition that the Turkish nation should engage with the latter at the outset of its project of modernisation. This distinction is particularly interesting as it frames the ideas of modernisation apart from the normative creation of this ‘modern Turkish nation’. Specifically, when independence as a Turkish civilisation is mentioned, Gökalp conceives the ultimate realisation of the Turkish nation as technologically advanced, modernised, and independent from the West. The use of Kızıl Elma particularly enunciates the fundamental cultural, political, and religious differences with Europe which Gökalp not only recognised to exist but actually classified as a positive. Essentially, Gökalp is asking us to consider this future modernised Turkish nation with advanced natural sciences and technology but not a part of European civilisation. Certainly, it may need initially to adopt the practices and trends of its European counterparts, but this is only during a transition period, after which a modern Turkey can adopt its own trends of modernisation. Turkification requires modernisation since Gökalp sees it as a requirement to face threats and maintain internal integrity. This necessitates imitation at first, followed by innovation. Hence, we see that Gökalp first proposed that the Turkish nation be in the European civilisation, recognising their technological superiority. This was to be followed by an independent Turkish civilisation, formed by its own tradition and philosophy.

CHAPTER VII: THE UNIFICATION

The rationale for such an extensive description of the terminology and concepts that Gökalp uses will become clearer in this section, as working on properly defined concepts ensures our critique is sound. It is evident from Gökalp’s writing and from the academic consensus that Gökalp’s ultimate goal was a Turkified Turkish state. The sketch above clearly indicates that Turkification is the primary goal of Gökalp’s thought; other programmes are a means to the end of Turkishness.

Considering this, the first line of practical critique to be made is the following: why, if the case of modernisation and Turkification are compatible, had the Ottoman Empire not successfully modernised itself, despite being a Turkish Empire.

Gökalp has little to say specifically about modernisation other than in terms of developing technology, beyond rejecting the possibility of the adopting of Western culture. He fails to explain why the Tanzimat reforms failed. However, we do see some elements of description in the modernisation thesis surrounding the Turkish people under the Ottoman Empire. In his critique, he provides an implicit sketch of what ought to be different in the reforms of the Republic. He notes that in the Empire, “there was no Turkishness left in the form of a people or a community; Turks were confined to the classes of civil servants and labourers” (Gökalp, 1918, p. 9). Gökalp blames the fact that Turks have been relegated below the elites of the Ottomans, arguing that “The Turkish people were deemed accountable for the persecutions by the Abdulhamid government” (Gökalp, 1918, p. 30). Gökalp’s description of the Abdulhamid government’s failure against the Turkish people is not entirely clear either, but the sale of Cyprus is one notable instance which was critiqued by Turkish nationalists. Cyprus had, and continues to have, a large Turkish population. Abdulhamid I’s government, faced with the failure of administering the island of Cyprus, agreed for Britain to take control in 1878. Many members of the Committee of Union and Progress (of which Gökalp was a prominent member) raised this as an example of a failed project in modernisation; by allowing Britain to administer the island, the Ottomans effectively prioritised relations with the West over their ‘native’ people. However, the question remains as to how Gökalp was to have this modernised

system, which emulated Western technological advancements while preserving the fundamental tenets of Turkism. Gökalp's reluctance to wholly embrace Western culture may appear contradictory to the ideals of the Turkish nation that he articulates in terms of its modernisation project. How can Gökalp advocate for a unique development of a Turkish nation rooted in a unique philosophy, while simultaneously aspiring to replicate the progress inherent in European technological advancements, which themselves are founded upon Western philosophical and cultural principles?

Heyd presented this critique, arguing that a fundamental shift in Turkish philosophy in line with the West needed to be made before advancements in technology could happen, and it is the 'regressive' nature of Turkish culture that previously failed to accommodate such developments. Here, the Orientalist understanding of culture is evident. A simple refutation can be made, in that there is nothing inherent within cultures and nations that allows for nor inhibits the development of technology (see Acemoğlu and Robinson, 2012 and also Braudel, 1979). A more valid critique of Gökalp's vision of modernisation is that the problem did not lie in Turkish culture's inability to accommodate technological development, but rather that the structure of the state was incompatible with such advancements. The Ottoman Empire's lack of a bureaucratic system, being devoid of centralised forms of banking, and other essential components necessary for capital to develop and modernisation to take place, was the cause of this incompatibility, and not culture. Technology would be difficult to develop without the necessary capital fuelling it. Gökalp pre-emptively attempts to rebut this critique, arguing that his idea of modernisation includes a drastic reformation of the structure of the state, even if his later writings returned to the Ottoman "political model based on a cult of personality with authoritarian implications" (Topal, 2017, p. 24). Gökalp was not naïve in his early writings when claiming that a statehood transformation needed to be constructed to partake in the project of modernisation. However, Gökalp fails to provide the specific material changes that need to be made to facilitate modernisation. Heper (1976) comments that the "phase of [bureaucratic] development in the Ottoman Empire's Islamic formulae [...] led to a relatively static conception of the functions of the state" (Heper, 1976, p. 506). This static structure of state functions hindered flexibility in adopting innovation, with an increasing "Islamic influence further [solidifying] the institutional pattern" (Heper, 1976, p. 510). The modern Turkish nation would have to contend with the inertia of this institutionally rigid structure in its reforms. This critique, therefore, only has merit if it focuses on the lack of specificity of Gökalp's proposals. The theme of Gökalp's modernisation thesis thus has no fundamental issues, simply lacking in detail on how this structure was to be changed/abolished.

A more substantive critique to level against Gökalp concerns the potentially difficult relationship between Islam and the idea of Turkism. While Gökalp argues that all components in his triad are equally complementary, Parla (1985) critiques this. He argues that Gökalp's conceptual vision of a unity of these three concepts is not as frictionless as he presents them to be. It has already been established that Islam for Gökalp has a social rather than a theological function. Yet even with this reduced role of Islam, the following quotation from Gökalp is considered by Parla as presenting Islam as a quasi-meta ideology:

Religion is the most important factor in the creation of national consciousnesses as it unites men through common sentiments and beliefs [...] genuinely religious men are those who have national fervour, and that genuine nationalists are those who believe in the eternity of faith (Gökalp, 1915, p. 75).

This then raises a significant question considering Gökalp's critical beliefs regarding Islam, his desire for a Republic, and the removal of the Caliphate. The assumption that Turkification was the primary motivator may not hold when confronted with this.

I argue, even in light of these comments, that Islam did not take a primary position over other programmes of reform for Gökalp. Heyd presents a similar argument; he states that Islam existed "for strengthening the Turkish nation, the interests of which are always dearer to him [Gökalp] than those of Islam" (Heyd, 1950, p. 95). Heyd's argument is valid. Gökalp's comments regarding the importance of religion should be taken in context with his purified view of Islam. This purified view advocated the importance of Turkish culture more than divine canon. There is no conflict here: as Islamic tradition ought to be sourced from Turkish culture in Gökalp's view. When understanding the idea of religion being the most important factor, we need to do so with the consideration of the context of how Gökalp understood Islam. Islamic canon was to be understood through the lens of Turkish culture and Turkish tradition.

We can continue to discuss the potential pitfalls that exist in Gökalp's practical politics and then attempt further clarification on their coherence. This, however, will not be as important as understanding what the philosophic essence of Gökalp's thought is. The philosophical underpinnings is the area of Gökalp's thought which the present scholarship has largely neglected to analyse. The most thorough approach in dealing with this aspect of Gökalp's thought is Parla's (1985). Parla notes that "Gökalp's political-social philosophy is social idealism, his general social theory is social solidarism, and his political theory is populist democracy" (Parla, 1985, p. 105). A unity in the triad of Turkification, Islamisation and modernisation is not the only union that Gökalp reaches for. Gökalp tries to "synthesizze a philosophical theory which in its departure is highly normative with a methodologically positivistic empirical and analytical theory; and which, to complete the full circle, is again infused with normative elements" (Parla, 1985, p. 107). Parla does not describe further the critique of contradictory thoughts, instead choosing to focus more on a Marxist corporatism critique (Davison, 1995). It is more crucial for the scholarship to extend Parla's critique regarding Gökalp's underlying philosophy.

When taking a conceptually constructive approach, we note Gökalp begins by setting out his aim, which is to develop the Turkish nation, Turkishness, and the Turkish state. This is an overtly normative, idealistic approach, which can be entirely tenable. Where the issue comes in is where Gökalp conducts a Durkheimian analysis of areas in which society and the state require improvement, which needs to be reconciled with the Rousseauian "radical egalitarian elements in his political and moral philosophy" (Parla, 1985, p. 113). Reformation in the manner described which claims to be based on this understanding of society, thus, cannot be realised. This issue is particularly potent in TIM.

The mechanisms that Gökalp provides for improvement or development in furthering his normative goals, Turkishness, are lacking in the structural capacity. Turkishness, in the way Gökalp describes it, is to be interpreted as egalitarian, democratic, and radical. Even when we consider the programme of cultural assimilation, which Gökalp was in favour of, what remains is a normative ideal of the Turkish nation as being communitarian in nature but individualistic in other cases, e.g., faith. The typologies of his system as being formed by içtimaî mefkûrecilik (social idealism) and içtimaî tesanütçülük (social solidarism) are indicative of Gökalp's underlying philosophy (Parla, 1985). This communitarian philosophy needs to be reconciled within the framework of individualistic proposals of Gökalp in his other reform proposals (Sariyannis, 2018). This becomes such an important issue in Gökalp's thought that practical critiques, such as those about the interaction between Islam and Turkism, become a minor concern. We encounter further complexity when introducing the framework of modernity. This is an area in which Gökalp recognises the issues facing the Ottoman Empire and, thus, the Turkish people. Gökalp provides limited commentary on changes, and instead discusses what should be done in very broad terms. While it is not expected for Gökalp to deal with the finer intricacies of a massive project of modernisation, his presentation still requires more detail. Gökalp does provide commentary on particular aspects of modernisation, these reflections are insufficiently radical to adequately address the social issues he analysed. For instance, he notes that the modern Turkish nation should strive to remove corruption in the state (Parla, 1985, p. 114), without elaborating further on any specifics. As such, we seem to find Gökalp's reforms and changes which he wished for are informed by a less critical interpretation of the Turkish condition.

Ultimately, these are the two main issues that need to be considered more. First, there are the contradictory philosophic roots of Gökalp's thought. Gökalp does not elaborate on the specific nature of how his view of a communitarian Turkish nation is to be reconciled with his idea of individual liberty in the Rousseauian manner. Secondly, there is the issue of difference between Gökalp's critique and his proposed reforms. This is particularly notable in his modernisation thesis, where Gökalp does not provide much detail as to how modernisation should occur, barring simple commentary regarding maintaining Turkish culture through modernisation. The overarching problem this article has demonstrated is that the problems of Gökalp's thought do not lie in the practical cohesiveness of his philosophy nor the potential friction between them. Rather, I have tried to show that when concepts are understood in context, whatever issues observed become not as substantive. What has been revealed is that Gökalp's arguments are simply lacking in specificity.

CHAPTER VIII: CONCLUSION

What has so far been discussed demonstrates that a closer study of Gökalp is needed, especially as his social analysis remains applicable to the Turkish nation today. His methodical and innovative analysis of Turkish society not only provided the foundation for further Turkish studies, but more importantly, played a foundational role in providing the political underpinnings for the revolutionaries of the Republic.

Given this important consideration, it is surprising to find that TIM has not received the level of scholarly analysis it deserves. It can be assumed that the scholarship viewed TIM as outdated and that *The Principles* was deemed to be the updated, modernised version of Gökalp's thought. I do not think this is the case. The two works are written with different assumptions. TIM concerns itself with a rich social critique centred around the reconciliation of the three concepts. It was written during the time of the Empire so we must understand it within that context. Conversely, *The Principles*, published shortly before the proclamation of the Republic, recognised the different contexts in which analysis needed to occur. While certainly there is overlap between the two, it would be wrong to consider TIM as simply a prologue to *The Principles*; there existed notable differences in understandings of Turanism and Islam between the two texts. A substantial amount of literature has been written regarding *The Principles*, unfortunately, an uncomfortable proportion has been polemic writings that hold little academic significance. This makes sense within the wider context of 20th century Turkish government policy, which was to promote the secular republic to a quasi-religious status. The interpretation we do have, however, recognises the importance of Gökalp's work.

In terms of the critiques presented in this article, it is important to note the two different forms. First, there are the practical critiques to which Gökalp's work has been subjected through the years. This article has demonstrated that the scholarship's disproportionate focus on the practical viability of his thought is not as crucial when contextualising his thought, as shown. When contextualised, we see that Gökalp's thought does not necessarily require reconciliation, nor does one concept subsume another, but rather each component of the triad is complementary to the aim of Turkism. The second line of critique is much more abstract and substantial. A reconciliation is only needed in Gökalp's thought when abstracting his practical reforms. While Gökalp does not explicitly discuss his philosophy and methodology, his practical recommendations are indicative of a certain philosophical underpinning. Yet, I think it is notable that the question of philosophic reconcilability is not substantive either. While indeed there are issues of political philosophy that are present, Gökalp's radical approach to reforming the Turkish nation in a pragmatic capacity excuses him. When we consider the essence of the concepts in the manner we have, we see that the potential contradictions are not fundamental. Rather, they originate from a lack of elaboration and clarification on Gökalp's part. In addition, I also do not think that the merits of Gökalp's work lie in his foundational political philosophy or in his methodology. To give an example, instead of placing Gökalp amongst thinkers like Hegel, Kant, and Rousseau, political philosophers that (claim to) formulate their theories *ab initio*, I would instead compare Gökalp to Lenin and Trotsky. Gökalp, foremost, was a tactician concerned primarily with a practical version of politics. While this does not absolve Gökalp of his shortcomings, it instead shows that we need to apply the critique relevant to the approach that Gökalp was taking. That approach was the answer to the question central to all of his works: 'How do we achieve true Turkishness?'

With these various considerations in mind, it is important to reiterate that the study of Gökalp's thought is still in its infancy. Interpretations and studies of Gökalp tend to utilise his work for an end, whether that be the Republican end of the Kemalists, or the fascist groups who transcribed *The Principles* into the Latin script. The disagreements discussed largely stem from Gökalp's system being a "relatively sophisticated and nuanced synthesis of elements that are difficult, but not impossible, to reconcile" (Parla, 1985, p. 104). What this article has done is add a new dimension to the scholarship of Gökalp, by considering his earlier works alongside his literature and poetry. It has also demonstrated that the question of compatibility or reconciliation, amongst the concepts that the scholarship focuses on, need not exist if we understand Gökalp's work in its entirety and in the contextual manner as presented. As such, I wish to conclude by considering that further research into Gökalp and other Ottoman political thinkers must first start by understanding the specific meanings of the words that each author uses. Meanings we might ascribe to concepts presently are likely not aligned with how thinkers understood them over a century ago. Contextual analyses must be at the centre of further research, not only in the study of Gökalp, but for all of Ottoman political thought.

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APPENDIX

Glossary

Örf: Traditional or customary practices within a given society, particularly significant in Islamic and Ottoman Turkish contexts.

Kızıl Elma: Literally translating as 'Red Apple', this is a Turkic mythological concept representing an idealised, utopian homeland or ultimate national aspiration.

Millet System: An Ottoman administrative structure allowing different religious communities considerable autonomy, especially in civil affairs.

Sufism: A mystical dimension of Islam, characterised by a personal, inner experience of faith rather than rigid adherence to dogmatic rules.

Tanzimat Reforms: A series of 19th-century Ottoman reforms aimed at modernising the empire's legal, administrative, and social structures along Western lines.

Turanism: A nationalist ideology advocating cultural or political unity among Turkic-speaking peoples across Central Asia.

Ummah: The global community of Muslims, understood generally as transcending ethnic and political boundaries.

Laïcité: A strict form of secularism, notably influential in Turkish republicanism, advocating separation of religion from public and political life. Also usually understood as the state taking an active role in what the majority religion is.